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Case Study

Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma Metastasis to the Breast and Axillary Lymph Nodes: A Case Report With Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Papillary carcinomas of the thyroid (PCT) are the most common type of well-differentiated cancers. These cancers usually remain localized in the thyroid gland. Distant metastases are rare and usually occur in advanced disease, usually in lungs, bones. Metastases to the breast are uncommon. We present a case of 84 years women who had a total thyroidectomy for a papillary thyroid carcinoma 11 years ago. She presented lump in left breast.

Mammography revealed a well defined, soft tissue confluent densities in the inner and lower left quadrant with irregular borders. The biopsy of breast lump was done. The Histopathological examination of the biopsy and immunohistochemistry staining concluded to metastatic papillary carcinoma of thyroid to the breast . The tumor's pathology and immunohistochemistry are discussed.

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INTRODUCTION:

Papillary carcinomas of the thyroid (PCT) are the most common type of well-differentiated cancers. They represent 80 to 85 % of malignant epithelial thyroid tumors (1). Eighty percent of differentiated thyroid carcinoma patients respond to total thyroidectomy, radioiodine-131 ablation and levothyroxine suppression treatment [2]. These cancers usually remain localized in the thyroid gland(3). A thyroid nodule or a neck mass is usually the first manifestation and less frequently regional lymph nodes metastases (1). Distant metastases are rare and usually occur in advanced disease, usually in lungs, bones(4). Metastases to the breast are uncommon. When combined with distant especially widespread metastases, the quality of life is compromised and the overall survival rate is significantly decreased (3). Reports of differentiated thyroid carcinoma with metastasis to breast are sparse. To our knowledge only 8 cases has been reported in literature. Five cases of PTC, 2 cases of follicular thyroid cancer, 1 case of hurthle cell cancer were reported. Among PTC with breast metastasis, two was

follicular variant, one tall cell variant, one was anaplastic carcinoma developing in PTC deposit in breast (1,5). In our case it was a classic papillary thyroid carcinoma.

OBSERVATION:

A 84 years women presented with lump in left breast. Her family history did not reveal any history of malignancy. 11 years ago, the patient had a total thyroidectomy for a papillary thyroid carcinoma. In the seventh year of follow-up after the initial operation, a bilateral cervical nodal metastases was identified. The patient underwent radiotherapy to the neck. On examination there was 2× 2 cm lump in lower inner quadrant of left breast without involvement of skin, pectoralis major muscle or chest wall with bilateral axillary lymphadenopathy. There was no cervical lymphadenopathy. Mammography revealed a well defined, soft tissue confluent densities in the inner and lower left quadrant with an irregular borders (Fig. 1).

Fig1: Mammography: confluent densities in the inner and lower left quadrant with an irregular borders, associated with skin thickening

The biopsy of breast lump was done. Histopathological examination of the biopsy revealed the papillary architecture with fibrovascular cores. Papillae lined by cuboidal cells, nuclei are overlapping with finely

dispersed optically clear chromatin and micronucleoli. Psammomatous calcifications were not seen; absence of DCIS (Fig 2,3).

Fig 2a (HEx 4) et 2b(HEx10) : papillary architecture with fibrovascular cores .

Fig 3: Hex 20: Papillae lined by cuboidal cells, nuclei are overlapping with finely dispersed optically clear chromatin and micronucleoli

Immunohistochemical positivity for Thyroglobulin (Fig. 4a, 4b) and negativity for GATA3 (Fig. 5). The

findings were consistent with metastatic papillary carcinoma of thyroid to breast.

Fig 4 a et 4b: Diffuse Positivity Of Anti-Wt1 Anti-Bodies

Fig5: Negativity Of Anti-GATA3 Anti-Bodies

DISCUSSION:

In previous studies, the ratio of breast metastases among all breast tumors has been reported as 0.5-2.0% (2). Diagnosis of a metastatic tumor should be considered in patients with known extramammary malignancies and when tumor morphology does not correspond to patterns typical for primary breast tumors(6). Papillary carcinomas of the thyroid are characterized by indolent and slow clinical course. It usually remains localized to the thyroid gland. Distant metastases are seen in a minority of patients and presence of distant metastases is the most significant poor prognostic factor for survival (7). The major sites of distant metastases are the lung and bone. Metastases to the brain, eye, breast, liver, kidney, muscle and skin are rare or relatively rare (3).

Metastatic progression of cancer is a multifaceted and complex process. In poorly differentiated or anaplastic thyroid cancer, both local and metastatic progression can occur rapidly, suggesting in these cases that the cancer cells have achieved a very aggressive non regulated state prior to metastasizing (8). However, in well-differentiated thyroid cancer, the presence of vascular invasion even in small tumors predicts the presence of distant metastases(9). These metastatic lesions are often located in the lymph nodes or lungs, are identified based on thyroglobulin elevations, are typically small and multiple, and tend to remain stable for years or decades. These data suggest that most

thyroid cancer distant metastases may occur early and remain dormant in the metastatic niche, especially in the lymph nodes and lungs, and further suggest that the latency between the metastatic event and subsequent progression is regulated by the cancer cells and the host environment(8). Secondary tumors on mammography appear as well-circumscribed masses without speculation (10), and the lack of tumor-associated acoustic shadowing has been suggested as a characteristic ultrasonographic feature of metastatic tumors in the breast [6]. Multifocality, especially with an unusual histological pattern, should consider the possibility of the presence of a metastatic tumor. The presence of a carcinoma in situ component would support a primary breast lesion [11]. Although some metastatic tumors can be differentiated from primary breast cancers in the presence of histopathological features. The histopathological features of metastatic tumors of the breast are frequently similar to those of primary breast cancers (12).

Immunohistochemistry plays an important role in the accurate identification of metastatic lesions. Primary breast carcinomas are positive for cytokeratin 7, and those of ductal origin express E-cadherin. The estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) are expressed in a subset of invasive breast carcinomas and in some other carcinoma. Thus, their presence or absence cannot determine whether a breast neoplasm is of metastatic origin (6). Immunohistochemistry for

TTF-1, Thyroglobulin and cytokeratin 19 established the diagnosis of metastatic papillary thyroid carcinoma to the breast(1). Reports of differentiated thyroid carcinoma with metastasis to breast are sparse. To our knowledge only 8 cases has been reported in literature. Five cases of PTC, 2 cases of follicular thyroid cancer, 1 case of hurthle cell cancer were reported. Among PTC with breast metastasis, two was follicular variant, one tall cell variant, one was anaplastic carcinoma developing in PTC deposit in breast (1). In our case it was breast metastases from classic papillary carcinoma of the thyroid. The soft clues that helped in alerting towards a metastatic spread to the breast other than classic nuclear features of papillary carcinoma of thyroid was the absence of DCIS albeit this can happen even in a primary invasive carcinoma of the breast. Clinically, metastatic cancers to the breast have been associated with poor prognosis, with most patients dying within 1 year of diagnosis (13).

In conclusion, the imaging findings of breast metastasis from thyroid carcinoma are nonspecific for metastatic or primary breast malignancy, but differential diagnosis should be included in the clinical setting of thyroid cancer recurrence. Especially in an elderly patient with a breast mass and a previous history of papillary carcinoma of the thyroid. Importantly, identifying mechanisms by which metastases escape from dormancy and progress in metastatic sites may be crucial in identifying appropriate targets for patients with progressive metastatic disease. These concepts and their potential impact on how we approach developing new therapies for thyroid cancer are the focus of this review.

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